

Community assessment of cancer drug combination screens identifies strategies for synergy prediction

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Abstract

In the last decade advances in genomics, uptake of targeted therapies, and the advent of personalized treatment has fueled a step change in cancer care. However the effectiveness of most targeted therapies is short lived, as tumors evolve and develop resistance. Combinations of drugs offer the potential to overcome resistance. The space of possible combinations is vast, and significant advances are required to effectively find optimal treatment regimens tailored to a patient's tumor. DREAM and AstraZeneca hosted a challenge open to the scientific community aimed at computational prediction of synergistic drug combinations and associated predictive biomarkers. We released a data set comprising ~11,500 experimentally tested drug combinations, coupled to deep molecular characterization of the respective 85 cancer cell lines. Of 150 submitted approaches, methods that incorporated prior knowledge of putative drug targets outperformed other approaches in predicting drug synergy across independent data. Genomic features of winning models revealed putative mechanisms of drug synergy for multiple drugs in combination with PI3K/AKT pathway inhibitors.

Introduction

Targeted personalized treatments based on a patient's genomic profile are important tools for cancer therapy. However, they remain imperfect and are further complicated by the genetic, non-genetic and clonal heterogeneity inherent of advanced cancers. Coupled with complex feedback and regulatory mechanisms, and dynamic interactions between a tumor cell and its micro-environment, multiple opportunities for drug resistance exist and any single therapy may be limited in its effectiveness¹. Furthermore, tumors that do initially respond to targeted agents often evolve to overcome their dependency on the drug target, acquiring drug resistance and leading to disease relapse. Drug combinations have the potential to overcome drug resistance and lead to more durable responses in patients. The molecular makeup of the cancer cell and the mechanisms driving resistance will influence the optimal combination of mechanisms to target¹⁻³.

High throughput preclinical approaches are critical in determining and evaluating effective combinations strategies. While empirical approaches are important in assessing the synergistic properties across drugs, the possible number of combinations grows exponentially with the number of drugs under consideration, and is further complicated when considering combinations across multiple disease and cellular contexts. Combination assays⁴ therefore remain a challenging and expensive proposition even when limiting focus and exploiting advanced robotic systems for *in vitro* drug screening. Computational approaches for predicting drug synergy are critical to guide experimental approaches for discovery of rational combination therapy⁵.

A number of approaches have been developed to model drug synergy using chemical, biological, and molecular data from cancer cell lines⁶. A key bottleneck in the development of such models is a lack of public data sets of sufficient size and variety from which to train computational approaches^{4,7,8}, particularly considering the diversity of biological mechanisms that may influence drug response.

To accelerate the understanding of drug combination synergy, DREAM Challenges (dreamchallenges.org) partnered with AstraZeneca and the Sanger Institute to launch the AstraZeneca-Sanger Drug Combination Prediction DREAM Challenge. DREAM Challenges are collaborative competitions that pose important biomedical questions to the scientific community, and evaluate participants' responses in a statistically rigorous and unbiased way, while also emphasizing model reproducibility and methodological transparency⁹. This Challenge was designed to explore fundamental traits that underlie effective combination treatments and synergistic drug behavior. The essential question posed to Challenge participants was how to predict synergistic activity from drug pairs using molecular data from baseline (untreated) cancer cell lines, chemical information, monotherapy response data, and/or *a priori* knowledge of cellular network and pathway data. This question is clinically relevant as predictive features may feasibly be measured prior to treatment to direct therapeutic choice, and so differentiating from prior challenges related to drug combinations¹⁰. As the basis of the Challenge, AstraZeneca shared ~11,500 experimentally tested drug combinations on 85 molecularly characterized cancer cell lines.

The Challenge was structured to address the following translational questions: (i) how to predict whether a known (previously tested) drug combination will be effective for a specific patient, (ii) how to predict which new (untested) drug combinations are likely to yield synergistic behaviors in a patient population, and (iii) how to identify novel biomarkers that may help reveal underlying mechanisms related to drug synergy. In this manuscript, we report on the results of this Challenge where we have identified novel and performant methods using a rigorous evaluation framework on unpublished data. Additionally, we describe the details of these approaches, as well as general trends arising from the meta-analysis of all submissions. Finally, we identify the mechanistic commonalities evident across predictive feature used to reveal genomic determinants of synergistic responses between multiple receptor tyrosine kinase and PI3K/AKT pathway inhibitors.

Results

1. A high quality data set covering diverse disease and drug combination target space

We collated a combinatorial drug sensitivity screen comprising 11,576 experiments across 85 cancer cell lines (Supp. Fig. 1). This dataset included cell viability response measurements to 118 chemically diverse compounds, and estimated synergy scores for 910 pairwise drug combinations with high reproducibility (Supp. Fig. 2; see Methods). Information on the compounds included, where available, their chemical properties and putative drug targets. We also acquired molecular data on these same cell lines, including somatic mutations, copy-number alterations, DNA methylation, and gene expression profiles (Fig. 1A - C) measured before drug treatment¹¹.

The 85 cell lines are predominantly derived from tumors of the breast (N=34), lung (N=22), bladder (N=14), and the gastro-intestinal tract (N=12) (Fig. 1D). Synergism for drug combination experiments were measured using the Loewe model, defined as increasing cell death beyond the expected additive effect of the individual compounds (see Methods). Drug synergy levels varied across disease types (Fig 1D); in particular lung cell lines had over two-fold higher mean synergy than breast cell lines (p -value $<7e-27$). Of the 118 compounds tested, 59 were targeted therapies against components of oncogenic signaling pathways (see Methods), 15 of which target receptor tyrosine kinases (RTKs), 22 target PI3K/AKT signaling, and 9 target MAPK signaling (Fig. 1E). Across the pair-wise drug combination experiments, 88% (N=797) of the unique pairs had drug targets within the same pathway and demonstrated markedly overall higher synergy levels (17.3 vs 7.3, p -value $<2e-18$) than the remaining 12% (N=113) whose drug targets were defined to be in different pathways. As part of the Challenge design, we ensured that drug targeted pathways and cancer types were proportionally distributed across sub-challenges and training/test data sets.

2. Challenge outcome: Participants reached the upper limit of prediction accuracy using mostly genomic data.

The Challenge was divided into two primary sub-challenges. In sub-challenge 1 (SC1) participants were asked to predict synergy scores for drug-combinations for which training data on those same combinations were available. In sub-challenge 2 (SC2), participants were asked to predict synergy status on drug combinations for which no training data was provided, thereby requiring participants to infer synergy using transferrable data/knowledge patterns identified from previously seen independent compound pairs. SC1 was further subdivided into two parts: SC1A allowed the use of all available data for model prediction, while SC1B limited data use to just mutation and copy number variation (mimicking current clinical assay feasibility). SC1A received submissions from all 76 teams, 62 for SC1B and 39 for SC2. As scoring metric we used the average weighted Pearson correlation between predicted and known synergy values for SC1, and both the $-\log_{10}(p)$ from a 3-way ANOVA and balanced accuracy (BAC) for SC2 (see Methods).

969 participants of diverse geography and training registered for the Challenge (Supp. Fig. 3A,B). Across all teams, mean performance scores were $R=0.24$ and $R=0.23$ (weighted

Pearson correlation) for SC1A and SC1B respectively, and $-\log_{10}(P)=10.6$ (3-way ANOVA) for SC2. Teams showed a small decrease in performance for SC1B, Δ primary metric = 0.03 ($P=0.007$), compared to SC1A (Figure 2A; Supp. Fig. 3C,D). While teams employed many differing methodological approaches to modeling drug synergy - including regression, decision trees, random forests, Gaussian processes, SVM, neural networks and others (Supp. Fig. 4A) - algorithm class showed little relationship to performance (Supp. Fig. 4B). We observed that participants submitting to all sub-challenges rather than just one tended to do better (Supp. Fig. 3E). The top winning team in all three sub-challenge was *Yuanfang Guan* (Y Guan) with primary metrics of 0.48, 0.45 and 74.89 in SC1A, SC1B, and SC2, respectively. Based on the primary metric in SC2, Y Guan performed considerably better (>5 Bayes Factor, based on bootstrapped metrics' comparisons, see Methods) than other teams (Figure 2B). All performance statistics and team rankings are available at the Challenge website (<https://www.synapse.org/DrugCombinationChallenge>).

To benchmark the performance of teams in the final rounds of SC1A/B and SC2, we established upper and lower bounds of performance. We defined the lower bound as the null model, *i.e.* random permutation of the synergy data across each cell line (see Methods). The upper bound was estimated using biological (experimental) replicates. We observed that 83%, 85%, and 94% of submitted models performed better than random (5% FDR, see Methods) for SC1A, SC1B, and SC2, respectively. Team performances varied widely, but remarkably the top 15 models submitted to SC1A reached a performance level comparable to the noise level observed in the biological replicates (Figure 2A), as did the top 13 models in SC1B. Proportionally fewer teams performed at the level of replicate experiments in SC2 based on the balanced accuracy (BAC), with North Atlantic Dream (NAD) coming closest to this bound (BAC=0.688; Figure 2C).

Given the limited performance of SC2, we assessed whether an ensemble method - based on an aggregation of all submitted models - could yield a better overall model, a phenomenon called "wisdom of the crowd"^{9,12}. We used a Spectral Meta-Learner (SML)¹³ approach, and observed a marginal improvement in performance (BAC=0.693) over the best performing individual team (BAC=0.688) and an ensemble of any number of randomly chosen models (Figure 2D). In SC2, SML ensembles including poorly performing models can achieve > 0.65 BAC.

3. Increasing performance using biologically meaningful features

Top performing teams (DMIS, NAD, and Y Guan) filtered cell line molecular features based on *a priori* cancer association (see Methods). These teams also consolidated pharmacological and/or functional pathway information associated with the molecular drug target, enabling one drug's model to learn from data generated for another drug with the same target (Y Guan¹⁶ and NAD^{14,15 16}).

To analyze each feature type's importance, particularly whether incorporating molecular features and chemical/biological knowledge can increase prediction accuracy, we re-engineered the DMIS and NAD models to use only cell line and drug labels as input features in SC1B (Figure 3, see Methods). Using these models as baseline predictors, we were then able to iteratively substitute or add specific molecular features or external data sources (e.g.

pathway/network information) to assess their importance in improving prediction (Figure 3A and 3B). Surprisingly high primary metrics were found for the baseline models (NAD 0.32, and DMIS ?) highlighting that drug and cell line labels alone hold predictive information. Drug target was the only feature to improve performance when swapped with drug or cell line labels (Figure 3A, $P=0.012$), and removing both drug label and target resulted in the highest performance drop (-0.17, Figure 3B). This result highlights the predictive value of the transferrable biological information encoded within drug target that is not available from unique drug labels. Mutational and copy number variation (CNV) data can similarly encode cell line label. However, where mutation data improved performance when replacing cell line label, replacement with CNV decreased performance significantly (Figure 3A, $P=8.8 \times 10^{-6}$). Importantly, in all cases additional feature data increased performance when added to the baseline model, confirming that addition of biologically meaningful information truly adds to the model performance (Figure 3A, $P=0.009$, 0.009 , 0.002 , 0.008 , 0.021 adding drug target, 3 different pathway based and mutation features respectively). Ensembles of different feature sets improved prediction most when collectively increasing coverage of biological (pathway) complexity, leading to substantial increases in model performance (Figure 3A, $P=1.2 \times 10^{-6}$).

4. Network connectivity of drug targets influences predictability.

While a global performance metric applied to all cell-lines and drug combinations provides a broad assessment of model prediction accuracy, we hypothesize that some models may be optimized for certain sub-classes of combinations and/or tumor types. We assessed the Pearson correlation between predicted and observed synergy scores for each combination in SC1A/B, and clustered teams by correlation of performance across combinations. Of the 118 combinations that had observed synergy scores >20 in more than one cell line, we identified 22 combinations predicted poorly by every participant (Figure 4A, see Methods), and over 50 combinations were defined as well predicted across all teams.

Surprisingly, the training data size and quality showed no notable difference between these universally poor and well predicted combinations (Supp. Fig. 5). Higher performance (average Pearson correlation 0.37 vs 0.25; $P=0.008$, Figure 4B) was observed for combinations inhibiting the PI3K/AKT pathway together with MAPK pathway, or apoptosis pathway with metabolism or receptor tyrosine kinases. Assessment of the interactions between drug targets and neighbouring proteins from *OmniPath*, a comprehensive compendium of literature-based pathway resources¹⁷, revealed no differences in the somatic alteration frequency for targets or their first neighbors between the poorly and well predicted combinations (Supp. Fig. 6A,B). We did observe a significant enrichment of well predicted combinations where both drugs' respective targets were downstream of a common neighbouring protein ($P=0.01$, Figure 4C), and conversely, we observed an enrichment of poorly predicted combinations where targets were both upstream ($P=0.03$, Figure 4C). There was no significant difference (Chi-sqr $P=0.44$) in *OmniPath* protein network distance between targets of well and poorly predicted combinations (Figure 4D).

5. Algorithms from top performing teams generalize to an independent drug screening data set.

We assessed the performance of top performing DREAM models on a smaller published screening experiment from O'Neill *et al*⁴. O'Neill *et al* applied a different measure of cell death compared to the DREAM drug screens (Cell Titer-Glo vs Sytox Green). A similar correlation was observed among technical replicates in the O'Neill *et al.* data set ($\rho=0.63$) compared to the AZ-DREAM data ($\rho=0.56$), however there was lower dispersion of synergy scores (Supp. Figure 2) and fewer instances of extreme synergy scores in O'Neill *et al.*

Focusing on cell lines and drug combination tests (Supp. Table 1) non-overlapping between DREAM and O'Neill *et al* data, we observed that SC1A models from NAD and DMIS outperformed a random model for all new combinations in the O'Neill *et al* screen (mean R = 0.07, $P < 0.01$) (Figure 5). Interestingly, no substantial performance increase was observed when independent model predictions were made on mutational profile from the 10 cell lines in common between the two datasets, nor the 30 similar combinations with similar chemical properties. As in the main challenge, combining these two models led to an improved prediction performance (Figure 5).

6. Biomarkers of synergy and clinical translatability

A typical shortfall of many machine learning algorithms is the lack of feature interpretability and experimentally testable logic-based rules. We took two approaches to identify biomarkers that may be predictive of drug synergies: a direct survey of participants through which predictive features were nominated for each drug pair and retrospective work focusing on results from two of the best performing teams NAD and DMIS to deconvolute features most impactful to model predictions. We focused on biomarker associations aligned to combinations for which the respective team had achieved a robust prediction accuracy (Pearson correlation > 0.5), with particular interest in the genetic biomarkers revealed through SC1B.

Monotherapy predictive biomarkers increase likelihood of observing synergy.

Although survey-submitted biomarker results varied in detail and depth (Supp. Table 2) common mutation and CNV markers were apparent across good predictions in SC1B, including EGFR, ERBB2, TP53, PTEN, PIK3CA or RB1. Synergy was commonly assigned to compound pairs targeting directly downstream of a mutated, amplified or over-expressed oncogenic driver, particularly those associated with monotherapy activity. To systematically test the association of monotherapy predictive biomarkers to combination synergy, we focused on Cancer Gene Census genes¹¹ for whom at least three of the 85 cell lines harbored genetic variants. The resulting 148 genes (45 mutated and 103 copy number altered) were then systematically tested for their association to monotherapy response of the 118 compounds (averaging replicates) across the 85 cell lines. We classified "monotherapy predicted" drug combinations as those for whom predictive features include at least one biomarker associated to either of the respective monotherapies (see Methods). We observed a significantly higher likelihood that a drug combination was synergistic for monotherapy predicted drug pairs (36%) compared to the overall synergy rate (27%) (t-test $P < 4e-11$, Figure 6A).

Biomarker associations to drug combinations are independently reproducible.

NAD and DMIS explored a total of 509 genomic traits after respective pre-filtering (Supp. Table 3) for SC1B. Features were ranked by their influence on model predictions for each of the well-predicted drug combinations (see Methods, Supp. Figure 7). We explored the top 5 ranked features for each of the well-predicted combinations from each team and consolidated drug-target centrally, giving a non-redundant list of 839 feature-to-combination associations. Filtering to results returned by multiple teams or with network/functional similarity between biomarker and drug target (see Methods) left 47 associations (21 with univariate FDR <35%, Supp. Table 4). 7 of these associations could be mapped to independent cell lines in the O'Neil et al⁴ data set, with an overall Pearson correlation between DREAM and O'Neil effect sizes of 0.32 (Figure 6C) showing a trend of reproducibility of synergy markers. Multiple validation criteria for quality and independent and *in vivo* reproducibility (see Methods)^{4,7,8} were then applied to prioritize 11 feature-to-combination associations (Figure 6B, Supp. Table 3), 7 associated with synergy and 4 with non-synergy.

Amongst the prioritized feature-to-combination associations were several genetic variants associated with synergistic responses to the combination of receptor tyrosine kinase (RTK) inhibitors with inhibitors of the downstream PI3K/AKT pathway. Amplifications or activating mutations in EGFR or ERBB2 consistently predicted synergy from RTK + PI3K/AKT pathway inhibition across multiple independent drugs and data sets (Figure 6B and 6D). Consistent with earlier observations, EGFR and ERBB2 mutations were commonly also predictive of respective monotherapy responses (Supp. Figure 8). Combinations inhibiting multiple points within the PI3K/AKT pathway also showed synergy in the presence of upstream activation from mutations in PIK3CA or deleterious events in PTEN (Figure 6B). Inhibition of the metalloproteinase ADAM17, known to influence RTK activity¹⁸, also showed synergistic responses in a common subset of cell lines when combined with inhibitors of PI3K, AKT or MTOR, with a notable exception of antagonism unique to PIK3CB/D selective inhibition in PIK3CA mutant cell lines (Figures 6B and 6E). Amplification and activating mutations in Androgen Receptor (AR) were also found to be associated with antagonistic effects for combinations targeting AKT and several MAPKs or RTKs, particularly MAP2K and IGF1R inhibitors (Figure 6B).

The biomarker analysis revealed that monotherapy markers improve likelihood of predicting synergy. Furthermore, the post-hoc analysis revealed various putative synergy biomarkers, particularly surrounding PI3K-AKT and ERK signaling.

Discussion

The results of the AstraZeneca-Sanger Drug Combination Prediction DREAM Challenge shed important light on the best strategies and limits to predict drug synergy. By evaluating predictions from a large number of teams, we were able to uncover important strategies for predicting drug synergy from molecular and chemical traits. As with most DREAM Challenges, we observed that the machine learning method itself has little impact on overall performance, and that selective incorporation of biological knowledge can help overcome issues of overfitting. Aggressive pre-filtering that considers drug targets and gene relevance

to cancer was successfully used by best performers to limit model complexity and to improve model generalizability. Despite the complexity of the problem, many teams achieved robust model performances, reaching the upper-bound of expected performance levels based on the observed variability of experimental replicates. This was further confirmed when top performing models were applied to an independent data set, demonstrating robustness to assay variability, and context heterogeneity.

For pre-clinical data analyses, biological hypothesis discovery and mechanistic understanding is a more directly actionable goal than predictive accuracy. Models derived in pre-clinical data may prove the concept of predictability, hence our emphasis in SC1B to show prediction with data readily retrievable from a patient. However these models are unlikely to translate without further training in clinical data since cell line panels do not comprehensively represent all tumor characteristics likely to be encountered in patients. That said, predictive features and biological rationale revealed by these models can be directly tested and used to drive further research. We put special emphasis on incentivizing and retrieving this information, but found this challenging within a format that focuses instead on performing well according to an objective scoring metric, that can be optimized with non-mechanistic models. Given that this and prior DREAM challenges indicate the machine learning method is less critical to performance than selection of biological features we strongly advocate for the use of learners with increased interpretability. In addition, accumulative small effects can explain good performance but are difficult to capture in post-hoc analysis with univariate test statistics, this could be further improved by integrating multiple genes.

A comprehensive assessment of the predictive value of monotherapy was not completed in the challenge format, in part due to initial miss-annotation of data, however retrospective analyses suggested it offered no significant improvement to well performing models (Supp. Fig. 9). Despite minimal predictivity from monotherapy itself as a feature, biomarkers aligning to respective monotherapy responses do show predictivity of combination benefit. Our observations that biomarkers aligning to monotherapy can influence synergy, and that more synergy is found where both drugs target downstream of a commonly interacting protein, advocate for a more biologically rationalized approach. Benefit may be derived by assembling a biomarker rationale by walking up- and downstream of the drug target to identify activated pathway components influencing monotherapy activity. Inference techniques PRECISE may also be considered where more universally predictive dynamic (e.g. transcriptional) signatures may first be used to identify a mechanistic rationale^{19,20,21,22} to which causative genetic or epigenetic events can then be aligned as predictive features^{23,24}. A surprising result of our challenge, however, suggested only modest improvement to prediction from inclusion of all data in SC1A vs only genetics in SC1B.

A notable absence from the Challenge was the use of mathematical, boolean or logic based mechanistic pathway modelling approaches²⁵⁻²⁹, likely due to the intensity of model creation. The dynamic nature of mechanistic models may offer an advantage by enabling consideration of the heterogeneity that exists across even apparently 'clonal' cell line populations²¹. The increasing availability of published pre-derived mechanistic models for many cancer relevant pathways may soon make such an approach more viable. Given the strong benefit seen from inclusion of prior-knowledge, and as text based artificial intelligence

technology matures, NLP and cognitive computational approaches to harness knowledge from world literature may also become of significant benefit.

Despite the limitations of the format, we were able to extract important insights to biomarkers for drug combinations. Given the dominance of RTK and PI3K/AKT pathway targeting agents in the challenge data, it was not surprising that these revealed some of our strongest combination-feature relationships. In multiple cases this aligned to a two-hit hypothesis targeting the activating driver with a downstream pathway component. These included synergies between EGFR and AKT inhibitors in the presence of PI3K/AKT pathway activation via EGFR mutations ³⁰, or AKT1/2 with pan-PI3K inhibitors in the presence of activating mutations in PIK3CA or upstream deleterious events in PTEN. In some cases the rationale for synergy was less direct, including combined AKT inhibition with EGFR inhibition in the ERBB2 mutant setting or FGFR inhibition in the EGFR mutant setting. Despite kinase domain homology between these RTK's off-target effects are unlikely to be revealed at tested concentrations, as reflected by low monotherapy activities. A likely explanation of this synergy may therefore be crosstalk and feedback signaling between the PI3K/AKT pathway and RTK's. Indeed previous reports suggest AKT inhibition drives activation of EGFR ³¹, providing a mechanism of escape that would be blocked with combined EGFR inhibition. These synergistic combinations targeting AKT with RTKs or MAPKs, have decreased effect and some antagonism in cell lines harboring activating mutations of AR ³²⁻³⁵. Feedback signaling resulting from AKT inhibition has been seen to drive AR activity which in turn can lead to the activation of the MAPK cascade ^{35,36}, attenuating respectively targeting drug activity.

Synergy observed between ADAM17 and PI3K/AKT pathway inhibitors may work through a similar mechanism whereby inhibition of ADAM17 driven proteolysis and shedding of RTKs¹⁸ stabilizes and increases their signaling through PI3K/AKT ^{37,38}. Notably ADAM17 predominantly influences RTK's other than EGFR/ERBB2¹⁸, and no benefit is seen in cells with mutations in these genes. Complementary anti-cancer effects from ADAM17 inhibition may, however, also result from its pro-tumorigenic role in other cancer hallmarks including cell survival, epithelial-mesenchymal transition and invasion. Interestingly ADAM17 inhibition showed a unique antagonism with PIK3CB/D selective inhibitors within the PIK3CA mutant setting. Reduced synergy may result from a lessened dependency on PI3K paralogues in the presence of constitutively activated PIK3CA, or reduced benefit from ADAM17 loss in the extreme luminal/epithelial physiology of PIK3CA mutants. The apparent antagonism, however, suggests feedback following PIK3CB/D inhibition enhances mutant PIK3CA expression/activity. Indeed PIK3CB inhibition has been shown to result in elevated expression and activity of PIK3CA ³⁹, and may also relieve the inhibitory effects of substrate competition or dimerization between PIK3CA and PIK3CB/D.

Looking forward, future challenges should extend the space of therapeutic combinations to include drugs targeting independent cell types such as subclonal tumor cell populations or cells of the tumor microenvironment and immune system³. It will also be critical to further address the question of how to optimize translation of preclinical results into the clinic⁴⁰. Where this challenge addressed prediction of synergy for known drug combinations, an ability to predict truly novel beneficial drug combinations should also be explored. Success in these areas will be dependent on the availability and access to large-scale data needed for model development and validation. Public-private partnerships - as exemplified by this

challenge and the generosity of AstraZeneca to share their private data with the research community - will be critical to future efforts. We believe that the pharmaceutical and biotech industry will greatly benefit from these pre-competitive collaborations that accelerate basic research insights, and their translation into the clinic.

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Authors contribution

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Competing financial interest

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Online Methods

Drug combinations screening

Cell suspensions are counted using a haemocytometer and cells are re-suspended in full growth medium containing Pen/Strep to a final density for different cell line densities and for different seeding densities into 384 well cell culture plate. A volume of cells as determined by cell count and dependent on cell type was added to each well of a Greiner 384-well plate using a Multidrop Combi liquid handler and then incubated at 37C and 5% CO₂ overnight in a rotating incubator. After seeding, plates were shaken to distribute the cells more evenly at the bottom of the wells and left to stand on the bench for 1hr to allow even settling of cells.

All plates were dosed with compounds solubilised in DMSO or PBS, or DMSO alone to provide comparable treatment and max control wells. Plates were dosed with compounds or DMSO only on an automated ECHO 555 acoustic reformatting system using the pre-configured DMSO and Aqueous calibration with DMSO normalised at final concentration of 0.14%v/v . After 5 days of incubation 5ul of 2uM Sytox Green working solution was added to each well of the 384-well plates (0.133uM final concentration) and the plates incubated for 1hr at room temperature. After incubation plates were read by the Acumen laser scanner to detect the number of Sytox Green stained cells. The total fluorescent intensity across the well was then read and the number of dead cells calculated by dividing this total fluorescence by the fluorescence of a single cell. The plates were re-read on the Acumen to give a total cell count. A live cell count was then determined by subtracting the dead cell count from the total cell count.

Quantifying combination synergy and antagonism

Monotherapy dose-responses of each drug in a combination was modeled as a sigmoidal curve and fitted to a classical Hill equation. In order to identify synergy or antagonism, an additive effect was first derived based on single agent dose-response curves using the Loewe model ([Fitzgerald 2006](#); [Geary 2013](#)). The Loewe model relies on the isobole equation which was solved numerically for all drug concentration values in order to calculate $A(a,b)$ and then derive $S(a,b)=E(a,b)-A(a,b)$. the synergy distribution $S(a,b)$ was summarized d by integrating $S(a,b)$ in logarithmic concentration space, what we called total synergy using Combenefit v1.31⁴¹

Molecular characterisation

The 85 cell lines were molecularly characterised, including:

1. Mutations from whole exome sequencing with Illumina HiSeq 2000 Agilent SureSelect ([EGAS00001000978](#))
2. Copy number variants from Affymetrix SNP6.0 microarrays ([EGAS00001000978](#))
3. Gene expression from Affymetrix Human Genome U219 array plates ([E-MTAB-3610](#))
4. DNA methylation from Infinium HumanMethylation450 v1.2 BeadChip ([GSE68379](#))

Mutations - Mutations were called with [CAVEMAN](#)⁴² and [PINDEL](#)⁴³ as reported in¹¹. Variants were provided without further filtering, including putative passenger mutations, germline variants and potential cell line artefacts, which are in total 75,281 mutations in 85 cell lines.

Copy number events - Copy number variants (CNVs) are called with the [PICNIC](#)⁴⁴ algorithm using the human genome build 38 as the reference. CNVs might be wild type, deletion or amplification of certain segments in a chromosome. One or multiple genes can fall within such segments. We reported copy number for the major and minor allele on gene and segment level.

Gene expression - Gene expression was processed as described in¹¹ including Robust Multi-array Average (RMA) normalisation with the R-package 'affy' (Gautier, Cope, Bolstad, & Irizarry, 2004). Gene expression for 83 cell lines across 17,419 genes (HGNC labels) was reported; no expression was available for MDA-MB-175-VII and NCI-H1437.

DNA methylation - We reported for 82 cell lines the *beta* and *M* values⁴⁵ for 287,450 probes; no methylation was available for the cell lines SW620, KMS-11 and MDA-MB-175-VII. In an additional processing step, CpG sites were compressed to CpG ilse with the definition from UCSC genome browser⁴⁶, resulting in a total of 26,313 CpG ilse based on either *M* or *beta* values.

Drug properties

The identity of all compounds was anonymised, but for all agents the putative targets are revealed. The gene names of the protein targets are listed with '*' denoting any character if the target is a protein family. Furthermore, for 58 compounds the Molecular weight, H-bond acceptors, H-bond donors, calculated octanol-water partition coefficient, Lipinski's rule of 5, and their SMILES (Simplified Molecular Input Line Entry Specification) are provided. Drugs were grouped into pathways and biological processes manually according to their protein targets (see drug info file in Synapse).

Challenge organization

The Challenge consisted of 2 Subchallenges, each with multiple rounds: a leaderboard, validation, bonus and collaborative round. Subchallenge 1 had 4 leaderboard rounds that lasted 8, 6, 5, and 5 weeks, while Subchallenge 2 had 3 leaderboard rounds that lasted 12, 7, and 5 weeks. Participants were given a leaderboard dataset to build a model and generate 3 prediction files per leaderboard round. Scores were returned to participants so that they can improve their model throughout these rounds for their one submission to the final round which was scored against a held out dataset. The final round lasted for 2 weeks which was then followed by a 9 week bonus round and 10 week collaborative round.

Challenge pharmacology data splits

In Subchallenge 1, participants were asked to predict drug synergy of 167 combinations in the panel of 85 cell lines. The synergy data of each drug combination was partitioned into 3 sets: a training data set (3/6-50%), a leaderboard set (1/6-16.7%), and validation set (2/6-33%) of treated cell lines. Subchallenge 2 leveraged data for remaining 740 drug combinations not overlapping with those used in Subchallenge 1, although data for some of the same compounds (in combination with different compounds), homologous compounds (i.e. same target, but different chemical structure), and cell lines were included. A leaderboard set (370 combinations) and a final validation set (370 combinations) were

randomly split, which are mutually exclusive from each other as well as from Subchallenge 1.

Challenge Scoring Metrics

Sub-challenge SC1, Primary Metric - The primary metric was an average weighted Pearson correlation (ρ_w) of the predicted versus observed synergy scores across each individual drug combination, i . The weight for a given drug combination i was $\sqrt{n_i - 1}$ where n_i is the number of cell lines treated with the drug combination. This resulted in the following primary metric for SC1A&B,

$$\rho_w = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N \sqrt{n_i - 1} \rho_i}{\sum_{i=1}^N \sqrt{n_i - 1}},$$

where $N = 167$ were the tested drug combinations.

Sub-challenge SC1, Tie-Breaking Metric - The tie-breaking metric was identical to the primary metric except that it was applied to the subset of drug combinations that have at least one cell line with synergy score $S_{ci} \geq 20$ in the held-out test set (S_{ci} = synergy score at cell line c and drug combination i). Neither the subset of drug combinations nor its size ($N = 118$) was revealed to participants prior to final evaluation.

Sub-challenge SC2, Primary Metric - The primary metric was a sequential three-way ANOVA, which tested the separation of held-out synergy scores by predicted synergy (= 1) and predicted non-synergy (= 0). In the sequential three-way ANOVA (type 1), we controlled for systematic drug and cell line effects, and evaluated variance explained by a given team's synergy predictions. We define the primary metric as

$$SA = -sgn \times \log_{10}(p),$$

where sgn is the sign of the effect size (positive or negative separation by prediction), and p is the p-value (F-statistic) computed from the ANOVA distinguishing predicted synergy (= 1) from predicted non-synergy (= 0) across all experimentally measured synergy scores.

Sub-challenge SC2, Tie-Breaking Metric - As the tie-breaking metric, we used balanced accuracy (BAC) using discretized synergy scores $S_{ci} \geq 20$

Applying the Tie-Breaking Metric - In each sub-challenge, we estimated a Bayes Factor (BF) using a paired bootstrapped approach to determine whether a team's score was statistically indistinguishable from another. In the event that a team's score were determined to be statistically equivalent, we then applied the tie-breaking metric. To estimate the BF, we sample with replacement from the M observations of the given sub-challenge and computing the primary metric (pm) for each team 1000 times. For a given team, T , K_T was computed by

$$K_T = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{1000} pm_{T,i} < pm_{best,i}}{\sum_{i=1}^{1000} pm_{T,i} \geq pm_{best,i}}$$

Where $pm_{best,i}$ is the bootstrapped primary metric at iteration i for the team with the highest primary metric (non-bootstrapped).

Assessing performance of individual combinations

Combinations defined as poorly predicted had an average predicted vs observed Pearson correlation across teams in the range seen with a random predictor (-0.25 and 0.25; Supp. Fig 8). In contrast, well predicted combinations had an average Pearson correlation across teams of above 0.5.

Independent validation on O'Neil et al Merck screen

In order to assess the utility of features and the predictability of the learning algorithms in new contexts, we provided the participants an independent large-scale oncology combination screen published recently ⁴. The O'Neil et al dataset consists of 22,737 experimental endpoints cover 583 doublet combinations across 39 diverse cancer cell lines. 38 experimental compounds and approved drugs were included in this combination screen using a 4-by-4 dosing regimen. Raw cell viability measures for each combination experiment were processed through Combenefit ⁴¹ and dose response surfaces were tested against the Loewe synergy model (same as in the Challenge). While there are 6 approved drugs, 49 targets, and 10 cell lines in common between the Challenge and O'Neil et al datasets, the total number of exact experiments (Compound A – Compound B – Cell line) overlapping is below 100, giving the participants a highly independent validation set for their prediction algorithms. This information was provided to best performing teams in the Challenge, along with a dictionary of curated chemical structures and putative targets for each. Prediction models were trained on the released Challenge dataset and made synergy score predictions on the O'Neil et al dataset. Metrics for SC1 and SC2 were used to assess prediction performance.

Individual Prediction Models

Full description and implementation of models used by teams in the final submission to DREAM can be downloaded from:

[www.Synapse.org/AstraZeneca Sanger Drug Combination Challenge Leaderboards](http://www.Synapse.org/AstraZeneca_Sanger_Drug_Combination_Challenge_Leaderboards)].

Top performing prediction models in SC1 and SC2 made use of genetic features relating to the gene targets of the drugs. Feature selection from the models enabled nomination of putative biomarkers for drug combination synergy (see Supplementary Material).

Ensemble Models

Subchallenge 2 participant models were aggregated using two types of ensemble models Spectral Meta-Learner (SML) and Random Agg. SML chooses predictions from n methods to aggregate based on an estimation of balanced accuracy for each method without using actual labels ^{13,47}. Random Agg is the traditional way that people aggregate models by giving equal weight to each method. We randomly pick n methods (do this 10 times) and for n methods we compute the average balanced accuracy and the error.

Monotherapy Biomarkers and Synergy enrichment

Monotherapy markers are the mutational status of genes, either mutated or copy number altered, from the pan-cancer binary event matrix (BEM) ¹¹, which separate the monotherapy response into sensitive versus non-response. The likelihood of separation was estimated with a Wilcoxon Rank Sum test. From most significant monotherapy marker to lowest in 0.1 steps of $-\log_{10}(\text{p-value})$, we accumulative evaluated the percentage of synergistic

combinations with at least one monotherapy marker. This analysis was bootstrapped 10 times with 80% of the pharmacology data.

Synergy Biomarkers

A short list of putative synergy biomarkers were derived from the 5 highest weighted features of well predicted drug combinations (Pearson > 0.5) from the two best performers NAD and DMIS. This gene-to-combination short list, was filtered for associations predicted by both teams, or genes biological related to the drug target defined as either the gene being the target itself, a short distance to it in OmniPath signalling network (2 molecules up- or downstream) or GO term similarity⁴⁸ larger than 0.7. This resulted in a list of 47 gene-to-combination associations that we further studied. A gene within this list is considered mutant if it was deleted, amplified (more than 7 copies) or mutated in any sense, resulting in an extended BEM¹¹. We calculated the p-value for each suggested association with an ANOVA correcting for tissue of origin and multiple hypothesis testing via Benjamini Hochberg. The effect sizes is the mean difference in synergy score between mutant and wild type cell lines.

For external validation of those putative biomarkers of synergy, we focused on drug combinations in O'Neil et al. 2016⁴, ALMANAC⁸ and additional experimental data from AstraZeneca (supplemental table 3). We validated biomarkers in two different contexts, (i) for cell lines overlapping with DREAM, considered as biological replicates, and (ii) cells non-overlapping for predictions on novel cell lines.

Literature evidence for the shortlisted combination-biomarker associations was identified through PubMed search. The aim was to identify published evidence of (i) the combination-biomarker association, (ii) the combination but not the specific biomarker, and (iii) either one of the targets and the biomarker association. The publications were further categorised into *in vitro*, *in vivo*, and preclinical studies. Publications that discuss the specific combination-biomarker association have been highlighted in red (Supp. Table 4). In summary, synergy biomarker were derived from best performer models, and highlighted based external validation as well as literature support.

Accession codes.
Data and full description of generation methods provided to all participants in this challenge can be downloaded from https://www.synapse.org/DrugCombinationChallenge

References

1. Holohan, C., Van Schaeybroeck, S., Longley, D. B. & Johnston, P. G. Cancer drug resistance: an evolving paradigm. *Nat. Rev. Cancer* **13**, 714–726 (2013).
2. Hanahan, D. & Weinberg, R. A. Hallmarks of cancer: the next generation. *Cell* **144**, 646–674 (2011).
3. Dry, J. R., Yang, M. & Saez-Rodriguez, J. Looking beyond the cancer cell for effective drug combinations. *Genome Med.* **8**, 125 (2016).
4. O’Neil, J. *et al.* An Unbiased Oncology Compound Screen to Identify Novel Combination Strategies. *Mol. Cancer Ther.* **15**, 1155–1162 (2016).
5. Al-Lazikani, B., Banerji, U. & Workman, P. Combinatorial drug therapy for cancer in the post-genomic era. *Nat. Biotechnol.* **30**, 679–692 (2012).
6. Bulusu, K. C. *et al.* Modelling of compound combination effects and applications to efficacy and toxicity: state-of-the-art, challenges and perspectives. *Drug Discov. Today* **21**, 225–238 (2016).
7. Gao, H. *et al.* High-throughput screening using patient-derived tumor xenografts to predict clinical trial drug response. *Nat. Med.* **21**, 1318–1325 (2015).
8. Holbeck, S. L. *et al.* The National Cancer Institute ALMANAC: A Comprehensive Screening Resource for the Detection of Anticancer Drug Pairs with Enhanced Therapeutic Activity. *Cancer Res.* (2017). doi:10.1158/0008-5472.CAN-17-0489
9. Saez-Rodriguez, J. *et al.* Crowdsourcing biomedical research: leveraging communities as innovation engines. *Nat. Rev. Genet.* **17**, 470–486 (2016).
10. Bansal, M. *et al.* A community computational challenge to predict the activity of pairs of compounds. *Nat. Biotechnol.* **32**, 1213–1222 (2014).
11. Iorio, F. *et al.* A Landscape of Pharmacogenomic Interactions in Cancer. *Cell* **166**, 740–754 (2016).
12. Marbach, D. *et al.* Wisdom of crowds for robust gene network inference. *Nat. Methods* **9**, 796–804 (2012).

13. Parisi, F., Strino, F., Nadler, B. & Kluger, Y. Ranking and combining multiple predictors without labeled data. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* (2014).
14. Gene Ontology Consortium. Gene Ontology Consortium: going forward. *Nucleic Acids Res.* **43**, D1049–56 (2015).
15. Kanehisa, M., Sato, Y., Kawashima, M., Furumichi, M. & Tanabe, M. KEGG as a reference resource for gene and protein annotation. *Nucleic Acids Res.* **44**, D457–62 (2016).
16. Babur, Ö. *et al.* Systematic identification of cancer driving signaling pathways based on mutual exclusivity of genomic alterations. *Genome Biol.* **16**, 45 (2015).
17. Türei, D., Korcsmaros, T. & Saez-Rodriguez, J. OmniPath: guidelines and gateway for literature-curated signaling pathway resources. *Nat. Methods* **13**, 966–967 (2016).
18. López-Otín, C. & Hunter, T. The regulatory crosstalk between kinases and proteases in cancer. *Nat. Rev. Cancer* **10**, 278–292 (2010).
19. Margolin, A. A. *et al.* Reverse engineering cellular networks. *Nat. Protoc.* **1**, 662–671 (2006).
20. Lefebvre, C. *et al.* A human B-cell interactome identifies MYB and FOXM1 as master regulators of proliferation in germinal centers. *Mol. Syst. Biol.* **6**, 377 (2010).
21. Fallahi-Sichani, M. *et al.* Adaptive resistance of melanoma cells to RAF inhibition via reversible induction of a slowly dividing de-differentiated state. *Mol. Syst. Biol.* **13**, 905 (2017).
22. Fakhry, C. T. *et al.* Interpreting transcriptional changes using causal graphs: new methods and their practical utility on public networks. *BMC Bioinformatics* **17**, 318 (2016).
23. Leiserson, M. D. M. *et al.* Pan-cancer network analysis identifies combinations of rare somatic mutations across pathways and protein complexes. *Nat. Genet.* **47**, 106–114 (2015).
24. Alvarez, M. J., Chen, J. C. & Califano, A. DIGGIT: a Bioconductor package to infer genetic variants driving cellular phenotypes. *Bioinformatics* **31**, 4032–4034 (2015).

25. Eduati, F. *et al.* Drug Resistance Mechanisms in Colorectal Cancer Dissected with Cell Type-Specific Dynamic Logic Models. *Cancer Res.* **77**, 3364–3375 (2017).
26. Kirouac, D. C. *et al.* Clinical responses to ERK inhibition in BRAF(V600E)-mutant colorectal cancer predicted using a computational model. *NPJ Syst Biol Appl* **3**, 14 (2017).
27. Klinger, B. *et al.* Network quantification of EGFR signaling unveils potential for targeted combination therapy. *Mol. Syst. Biol.* **9**, (2013).
28. Silverbush, D. *et al.* Cell-Specific Computational Modeling of the PIM Pathway in Acute Myeloid Leukemia. *Cancer Res.* **77**, 827–838 (2017).
29. Flobak, Å. *et al.* Discovery of Drug Synergies in Gastric Cancer Cells Predicted by Logical Modeling. *PLoS Comput. Biol.* **11**, e1004426 (2015).
30. Yi YW, E. *al.* Inhibition of the PI3K/AKT pathway potentiates cytotoxicity of EGFR kinase inhibitors in triple-negative breast cancer cells. - PubMed - NCBI. Available at: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/23601074>. (Accessed: 22nd June 2017)
31. Wei F, E. *al.* mTOR inhibition induces EGFR feedback activation in association with its resistance to human pancreatic cancer. - PubMed - NCBI. Available at: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/25654224>. (Accessed: 22nd June 2017)
32. Shi, X.-B., Ma, A.-H., Xia, L., Kung, H.-J. & de Vere White, R. W. Functional analysis of 44 mutant androgen receptors from human prostate cancer. *Cancer Res.* **62**, 1496–1502 (2002).
33. Gottlieb, B., Beitel, L. K., Nadarajah, A., Paliouras, M. & Trifiro, M. The androgen receptor gene mutations database: 2012 update. *Hum. Mutat.* **33**, 887–894 (2012).
34. Eisermann, K., Wang, D., Jing, Y., Pascal, L. E. & Wang, Z. Androgen receptor gene mutation, rearrangement, polymorphism. *Transl. Androl. Urol.* **2**, 137–147 (2013).
35. Carver, B. S. *et al.* Reciprocal feedback regulation of PI3K and androgen receptor signaling in PTEN-deficient prostate cancer. *Cancer Cell* **19**, 575–586 (2011).
36. Zhu, M.-L. & Kyprianou, N. Androgen receptor and growth factor signaling cross-talk in prostate cancer cells. *Endocr. Relat. Cancer* **15**, 841–849 (2008).

37. Meng, X. *et al.* ADAM17-siRNA inhibits MCF-7 breast cancer through EGFR-PI3K-AKT activation. *Int. J. Oncol.* **49**, 682–690 (2016).
38. Zheng, X. *et al.* ADAM17 promotes breast cancer cell malignant phenotype through EGFR-PI3K-AKT activation. *Cancer Biol. Ther.* **8**, 1045–1054 (2009).
39. Schwartz, S. *et al.* Feedback suppression of PI3K α signaling in PTEN-mutated tumors is relieved by selective inhibition of PI3K β . *Cancer Cell* **27**, 109–122 (2015).
40. Lopez, J. S. & Banerji, U. Combine and conquer: challenges for targeted therapy combinations in early phase trials. *Nat. Rev. Clin. Oncol.* (2016).
doi:10.1038/nrclinonc.2016.96
41. Di Veroli, G. Y. *et al.* Combenefit: an interactive platform for the analysis and visualization of drug combinations. *Bioinformatics* **32**, 2866–2868 (2016).
42. Stephens, P. J. *et al.* The landscape of cancer genes and mutational processes in breast cancer. *Nature* **486**, 400–404 (2012).
43. Ye, K., Schulz, M. H., Long, Q., Apweiler, R. & Ning, Z. Pindel: a pattern growth approach to detect break points of large deletions and medium sized insertions from paired-end short reads. *Bioinformatics* **25**, 2865–2871 (2009).
44. Greenman, C. D. *et al.* PICNIC: an algorithm to predict absolute allelic copy number variation with microarray cancer data. *Biostatistics* **11**, 164–175 (2010).
45. Du, P. *et al.* Comparison of Beta-value and M-value methods for quantifying methylation levels by microarray analysis. *BMC Bioinformatics* **11**, 587 (2010).
46. Kent, W. J. *et al.* The human genome browser at UCSC. *Genome Res.* **12**, 996–1006 (2002).
47. Jaffe, A., Nadler, B. & Kluger, Y. Estimating the accuracies of multiple classifiers without labeled data. in *Artificial Intelligence and Statistics* 407–415 (2015).
48. Wappett, M. *et al.* Multi-omic measurement of mutually exclusive loss-of-function enriches for candidate synthetic lethal gene pairs. *BMC Genomics* **17**, 65 (2016).

Figures

Figure 1: Drug combinations and cell lines profiled. (A) Molecular characterization of the cell lines included genetics, epigenetics and transcriptomics. (B) Participants were encouraged to mine external data and pathway resources. (C) Participants were provided the putative targets and chemical structures for $\sim\frac{1}{3}$ of cell lines to predict synergistic combinations. (D) The cell line panel contained 85 cell lines from 6 different cancer types. (E) The drug portfolio comprised approximately half oncogenic signaling targeting agents, and half cytotoxic compounds of which 14 were untargeted chemotherapies (F) Compounds split by the putative targeted pathway. (G) Sparse data was split into training set, leaderboard and independent test set for challenge 1 and 2 and color coded accordingly, see legend in panel G.

Figure 2: Performance of teams in the DREAM challenge. (A) Participant performance in SC1A and SC1B – the distribution of performance of random predictions was used to estimate a lower limit, and the distribution of synergy correlations between biological replicates were used to estimate the upper limit. (B) Participant performance ranked in sub-challenge 2 based on the primary metric, 3-way ANOVA. Distribution of bootstrap prediction performances for each team are shown by each boxplot with the dot showing their actual performance. (C) Participant performance plotted with upper and lower limits for SC2 based on the tie-break metric. Performance of random predictions were used to estimate the lower limit, and the performance of biological replicates were used to estimate the upper limit. (D) Ensemble models compared to the performance of individual models ranked from best to poorest performing in sub-challenge 2. SML is an ensemble of the best performing models based on estimation of their balanced accuracy. Random Agg. is an ensemble combining a random combination of models. Standard error of mean represented by error bars are estimated from 10 random splits of the data.

Figure 3: Feature impact. Drug target annotation is key in top performing algorithms, as is the meta information about variants including their functional impact and tumor driver gene status. (A) Cross validation based distributions of NAD primary metric of SC1B when replacing or adding drug/cell line label with respective features (baseline model has just drug and cell line label). * $P < 0.05$, ** $P < 0.01$, and *** $P < 0.001$ compared to baseline model (B) Heatmap of decrease in performance (average weighted Pearson correlation) of SC1B for DMIS support vector regression method when two feature types are removed at once (rows and columns).

Figure 4: Features of poorly and well predicted combinations. (A) Heatmap of Pearson correlation between observed and predicted synergy scores for 118 combinations across 73 teams participating in SC1A/B. Algorithms used by each team is marked in the matrix below. (B) Combinations of pathways targeted. Size of node is proportional to number of drugs targeting specific pathway and width of edges is proportional to the number of drug combinations. (C) Types of interactions between two drug targets for poorly and well predicted combinations. Boxplots show the difference in the proportion of interactions of each type for poorly and well predicted combinations (t -test). (D) Proportion of poorly and well predicted combinations for different network distances (minimum number of interactions in the OmniPath shortest path) between the targets of a drug combination.

Figure 5: Translatability of top performing DREAM models to an independent screen by O'Neil et al⁴. Performance of 1A models for predicting synergy scores in the O'Neil et al dataset by the best performing teams are plotted along with distributions of predictions from the random model and replicate experiments. Performance of predictions are shown for all experiments in the O'Neil et al data set, and three subsets of the data set; experiments that tested same cell lines as DREAM, tested similar drugs as in DREAM (one drug in the combination with the same target), and tested similar combinations as in DREAM (same targets for both drugs in the combination).

Figure 6: Post-hoc analysis of putative synergy biomarkers. (A) Enrichment of monotherapy markers lead to an enrichment of observed synergy. (B) Validation of biomarker predictions in new cell lines and independently screened drug combinations by O'Neil et al. 2016. (C) Synergy markers suggested by DMIS and NAD, when focusing on top weighted features from predictive models filtered for biological relatedness to drug targets, ****=5%, ***=20% and **=35% FDR. (D) Comparison of ADAM17 combined with PIK3CB/D against ADAM17 in combination with pan-PI3K3C inhibitor. (E) Network cartoon of PI3K signalling and role of ADAM17.